

IOT Based Wheelchair Fall Detection

A Project Submitted

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A project submitted to the Electrical and Electronic Engineering Department of the Engineering Faculty, **Port City International University** in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of Bachelor of Science in Electrical and Electronic Engineering.

Department of
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DECLARATION

This is to certify that this project is our original work. No part of this work has been submitted elsewhere partially or fully for the award of any other degree or diploma. Any material reproduced in this project has been properly acknowledged.

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APPROVAL

The Project titled “**IOT Based Wheelchair Fall Detection**”

Has been submitted to the following respected members of the Board of Examiners of the department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of Bachelor of Electrical and Electronic Engineering on July, 2020 by the following student and has been accepted as satisfactory.

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ABSTRACT

Fall detection is major challenge in healthcare domains. For elder people, it is very difficult to manage when they are fall from wheelchair. It is very serious and leads to especially healthcare issues. So we have developed a IoT based fall detection system which involves, if a person falls from the wheelchair, it will turn ON the buzzer and alert the people around that place, and the fall detection will updated in the cloud. Here we are using GSM module to connect with the mobile SIM network which will receive an instant fall detection message. For detecting the fall detection we are using accelerometer and gyroscope sensors. If the sensor values exceeds the particular threshold value , it will detected as fall, the buzzer will ON and also the message will report the occurrence of an accident and sends information of the location of accident to the family members of the patient through the emergency contact numbers.

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Introduction

In our society, yearly there are a significant number of cases where senior citizens and physically handicapped person fall down from wheelchair in their residential area. When our family members come to old age, it also becomes essential to monitor them for their in-home health and safety. Although they dwell in home, because of illness and weedy joints they have a big threat of falling down in any corner of home premises. In such circumstances, it becomes significant to recognize if an elderly person or a physically handicapped person has fallen so that he/she can get quick help on time. Currently CCTV Camera-based monitoring systems are in existence but these systems are very expensive. Common man cannot afford such system. For these reasons we propose a novel, smart and cost-effective fall-detection system by merging latest technology as Internet of Things and existing algorithms based fall detection. This system uses low-cost accelerometer and gyroscope sensors to detect person's fall-like movements. Gyroscope sensor is a smart device can be easily fixed on the cap of the patient. System will be watching keenly for fall detection and unexpected motion changes in targeted person. An unexpected abrupt change with peak in the system is treated as a fall. In case of the person did not fall and alarm was false, then the system will have a provision to stop the alert within 5 seconds. If within stipulated time, person does not press stop button, system will consider it's as fall- activity and automatically sends an alert message via GSM to victim's take-givers for quick medical help.

1.2 Objectives

1. To help the patient immediately.
2. To control the system by using wireless communication.
3. To reduce the injury in shortest time.
4. To make sure our patient is safe or not at home or anywhere else without under being watched.
5. To inspire the idea of using modern wheelchair.

1.3 Motivation

Intelligence and awareness of human activity is a key exploration point for a broad field of

extensive utilization such as remotely monitoring the health of the elder people, detecting the falls and ambulatory monitoring. Despite research done in past, the computer vision techniques which are being used nowadays create a problem such as confidentiality. In this paper a fall detection system is designed to monitor the elder people or the physically handicapped patients that are based on the gyroscope sensor and GSM technology, operating through indoor and outdoor tracking using the embedded system with the thresholds. The falls can be detected of the elder people who are living alone in the home and the person who is handicapped can have certain incidents like falling so to monitor the elder people activities this paper presents the gyroscope sensor and the GSM technology using this technology the activities of the elder people or physically handicapped patients can identify.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Literature Review:

A review estimated that 0.2% of serious wheelchair accidents result in death although there are limited data about fatal wheelchair accidents. In a search of death certificates from 1973 to 1987, researchers identified and described 770 wheelchair-related deaths. The cause of death was categorized, sometimes with more than 1 category applicable. Of these 770 wheelchair-related deaths, 595 persons (77.4%) had a fall from their wheelchairs or tipped over. Of 85 deaths (11%) caused by environmental factors, stairs were implicated in 51 (60%). Other wheelchair-related deaths were due to fatal burns (6.2%) and asphyxia due to restraints (5.7%).^[1]

In the United States, an estimated yearly average of 36,559 nonfatal, wheelchair-related accidents occur that require emergency department attention.^[2]

Tips and falls were identified in one study as the most common form of accidents, resulting in fractures (45.5%), lacerations (22.3%), and contusions/abrasions (20.1%).⁷ Another study reported that the majority of accidents occurred while using a scooter (52.8%), compared to powered wheelchairs (24.6%) and manual wheelchairs (22.6%), and that many of the accidents occurred outdoors or on ramps.^[3]

In summary, there is approximately one wheelchair-related death per week in the United States, the vast majority of which are due to falls. Much of the research, however, has failed to distinguish risk factors by etiology. To design the most effective interventions to prevent wheelchair-related falls, an in-depth understanding of the causes, antecedents, and consequences is needed.

Wheelchair characteristics have been implicated in accidents. For example, wheelchairs that offer variable rear axle position can provide more efficiency in propelling by placing the axle close to the system center of gravity, but this practice increases the risk of tipping over backwards.

The use of smaller, harder front wheels maximizes maneuverability by shortening the overall length of the wheelchair but contributes to forward tips and falls by being more susceptible to

being stopped by uneven terrain.¹ The use of negative camber (angling the rear wheels so that the bottoms of the wheels are farther apart than the tops) is associated with a 3.91 times increased risk of sustaining an instability incident, because negative camber moves the center of gravity of the occupied wheelchair backward and causes a backward tilt of the frame.^[4]

Caregivers also may be a contributing factor in wheelchair-related accidents, with resultant injuries to the patient or the caregiver. Adverse events can occur while staff personnel are performing transfer tasks for patients who are agitated, fearful, unsteady, or too weak to perform the task independently. Tripping over the front rigging (ie, foot rests, leg rests) is a common source of injury to caregivers as is leaning over the back of the wheelchair to engage or disengage the wheel locks. Attempts at repositioning patients in their wheelchairs can also pose a serious threat of back, neck, and upper extremity injury to caregivers.

Lack of proper wheelchair prescription and training has been cited as a contributory factor in wheelchair-related accidents and injuries. There is evidence that wheelchairs are often selected without professional input and that self-selected wheelchairs have a disproportionate percentage of problems with fit and function.^[5]

Poorly or improperly maintained equipment is a factor for increased risk of wheelchair-related accidents.¹⁵ In a study conducted in 1997, wheelchair component failures represented 84 incidents, 33% of the sample, with twice as many failures occurring in powered chairs as manual chairs. These component failures resulted in the wheelchair tipping or falling and caused 17 injuries requiring medical attention and 1 injury requiring hospitalization.^[6]

Persons with SCI have reported wheelchair-related falls incurred during transfer tasks and reaching while seated in the wheelchair.¹⁶ Other activities that may contribute to wheelchair-related falls include participating in certain wheelchair sports, operating a van lift, and propelling a wheelchair with both elevating leg rests in the fully extended position.^[7]

Regarding the physical environment, more than twice as many accidents occurred outdoors than indoors.³ Curbs, ramps, uneven terrain, stairs, and wet or icy surfaces have been implicated in wheelchair-related accidents.^{1,2,5} Persons with SCI have reported wheelchair-related falls incurred while propelling over uneven terrain.¹⁶ In nursing homes, environmental hazards, including improperly maintained or fitted wheelchairs, accounted for 16% of falls.^[8]

Wheelchair-related accidents can occur during wheelchair transfers, propelling over uneven terrain, reaching for objects, and maneuvering curbs or stairs. Tipping and falling are the most common form of incidents. Among persons with SCI, lower extremity fractures accounted for 93% to 97% of injuries sustained in wheelchair-related accidents.¹⁶ Other investigators reported a series of 267 fractures in 160 individuals with SCI. The sample included persons with paraplegia (63%) and tetraplegia (37%). Most of these fractures occurred in the vicinity of the knee joint, with an even distribution between femoral and tibial fractures.^[9]

In a study of 577 community-dwelling wheelchair users, 57.4% reported that they had completely tipped over or fallen from their wheelchairs at least once, and 66.0% reported having partially tipped. Of the falls and tips reported, 46.3% were in the forward direction, 29.5% backward, and 24.2% sideways.^[10]

In long-term care settings, problems related to wheelchairs include falls, trips, collisions with objects or other persons, and de facto use as a restraint.¹¹ In addition, among elderly long-term care residents, the majority of wheelchair-related injuries appeared to be connected with failed attempts to independently transfer into or out of a wheelchair and leaning forward.^[11]

In a study of incidents reported by 109 community-dwelling participants, subjects' disability types included SCI quadriplegia, SCI paraplegia, cerebral palsy, and neuromuscular diseases. Tips and falls were the cause of 66% of accidents, and injuries of all types in this group were distributed fairly evenly between manual and powered wheelchair incidents. Reported wheelchair-related injuries were 117 cuts and bruises, 29 fractures, 19 head injuries, 15 muscle and tendon injuries, 1 dental injury, and 13 unspecified injuries.^[12]

Falls from wheelchairs are costly to both individuals and businesses in terms of costs paid by Medicare, Medicaid, private insurance companies, and hospitals. Medical bills incurred in wheelchair-related falls, including rehabilitation, are often between \$25,000 and \$75,000 (G. Dugas, written communication, 2002). A fracture in a patient with SCI usually results in a 4- to 8-week hospital stay with significant time on bed rest, resulting in the inevitable loss of strength due to immobilization. Blood clots also are associated with fractures. In non-SCI elderly patients, wheelchair falls may result in a hip fracture and the attendant surgery for internal fixation, which has a significant mortality.^[13]

People who use wheelchairs face a range of physical, social, and economic barriers to regular participation in their communities. These barriers may be more acute in countries such as Bangladesh which are affected by poverty and often lack the physical infrastructure or resources necessary to create inclusive or accessible environments.

The World Health Organization (2010) indicates that approximately 65 million people worldwide require the assistance of a wheelchair. Strong evidence from around the world demonstrates that people who use wheelchairs face a range of physical, social, and economic barriers to regular participation in their communities (e.g. Schonherr et al, 2005; Balbale et al, 2017). These barriers may be even more acute in countries affected by poverty, such as Bangladesh, as these countries often lack the physical infrastructure or resources necessary to create inclusive or accessible environments for wheelchair users. Global human rights treaties, such as the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UN CRPD) have emphasised the importance of “identification and elimination of obstacles and barriers to accessibility”(United Nations 2006, Article 9)for persons with disabilities. Many countries have espoused this commitment to identification and removal of barriers at the national and local levels through national policies on disability. In spite of policy commitments, disparities remain for wheelchair users globally, particularly in the developing world(Burns and O’Connell, 2012). In order to translate policy commitments to action, research may assist in the identification of barriers at a local level and in the communication of these barriers and remedies to policy-makers and other relevant stakeholders. People with disabilities themselves are in the best position to identify these factors, as they encounter the barriers and facilitators to inclusion on a daily basis (Newman and SCI Photovoice Participants, 2010).

This manuscript details the results of a participatory action research (PAR) project that aimed to identify barriers and facilitators to accessibility for people who use wheelchairs in Bangladesh, and to take action to remedy barriers and promote facilitators identified.

Bangladesh is one of the most densely populated countries in the world (1070 population/km²). Recent reports indicate it has a gross national income (GNI) per capita of US\$1,314 (National Institute of Population Research and Training and International -NIPORT, Mitra and Associates, 2016). Bangladesh has a relatively high incidence of spinal cord injuries and other disabilities - due to falls from heights, traffic accidents, and physically demanding and hazardous occupations - that require the assistance of a wheelchair for mobility (Rahimi-Movaghar et al, 2013; Villanueva et al, 2017). The Government of Bangladesh has demonstrated strong public support for the inclusion of persons with disabilities in mainstream

society. This support includes a national policy on disability, the Persons with Disabilities' Rights and Protection Act 2013, which is in line with the principles of the UN CRPD (Women with Disabilities Development Foundation, no date). Additionally, Prime Minister Sheikh Hasina has made numerous public proclamations related to the rights of persons with disabilities, including outlining government efforts for greater identification of people with disabilities and provision of social protections and financial support, along with access to health and education facilities (News Bangladesh, 2016).[14]

This study provides an insight into some of the barriers and facilitators faced by wheelchair users in Bangladesh and the effect that these barriers have on their lives. However, this study is only the initial effort, since the goal was not only to identify and study these issues but also to use the gathered information to promote social change on the ground. In addition to sharing the results with an academic audience, the plan is to disseminate the results of this study in a range of accessible formats for stakeholders and change-makers, including people with disabilities, community members, and policy-makers, through a series of photo exhibitions, posters, and discussions in Dhaka and surrounding areas. It is hoped that future research and action will encourage more people to get involved in removing barriers for people with disabilities in Bangladesh and globally. Everybody has a responsibility to act.

CHAPTER 3

COMPONENTS OVERVIEW

3.1 Introduction

In this chapter we discuss about the hard ware software. This document describes the theoretical information of this project. All functional components of this project are described in great detail. This document can help us quickly understand all device interface specifications. This project consists of an Arduino Nano, Sonar sensor, Node MCU, LCD, Google database, wire. All the details of this equipment is discuss in the below.

3.2 Arduino Nano

Arduino Nano is a small micro controller, it controlled my two micro controllers, one for connection with computer, and another one is main microcontroller. It has on board computing system 32 kb flash memory is main storage for control gpio.

Fig 3.1: Printed circuit board of Arduino Nano

3.2.1 Technical Specification

Main board: Atmel ATmega168 or ATmega328.

USB Serial adapter: CH340

Running Voltage (logic level): 5 V.

Max input (recommended): 7-12 V.

GPIO Digital I/O Pins: 14 (of which 6 provide PWM output).

GPIO Analog Input Pins: 8.
 DC Current per I/O Pin: 40 mA.
 Memory: 16 KB
 SRAM: 1kB
 EEPROM: 512 b
 Clock Speed: 16 MHz

Fig 3.2: Pin diagram of Arduino nano
Pins 1 to 3

Table 1: 3.2.2 Arduino Nano Pin Description

Arduino Nano Pin	Pin Name	Type	Function
1	D1/TX	I/O	Digital I/O Pin Serial TX Pin
2	D0/RX	I/O	Digital I/O Pin Serial RX Pin
3	RESET	Input	Reset (Active Low)
4	GND	Power	Supply Ground
5	D2	I/O	Digital I/O Pin
6	D3	I/O	Digital I/O Pin
7	D4	I/O	Digital I/O Pin
8	D5	I/O	Digital I/O Pin

9	D6	I/O	Digital I/O Pin
10	D7	I/O	Digital I/O Pin
11	D8	I/O	Digital I/O Pin
12	D9	I/O	Digital I/O Pin
13	D10	I/O	Digital I/O Pin
14	D11	I/O	Digital I/O Pin
15	D12	I/O	Digital I/O Pin
16	D13	I/O	Digital I/O Pin
17	3V3	Output	+3.3V Output (from FTDI)
18	AREF	Input	ADC reference
19	A0	Input	Analog Input Channel 0
20	A1	Input	Analog Input Channel 1
21	A2	Input	Analog Input Channel 2
22	A3	Input	Analog Input Channel 3
23	A4	Input	Analog Input Channel 4
24	A5	Input	Analog Input Channel 5
25	A6	Input	Analog Input Channel 6
26	A7	Input	Analog Input Channel 7
27	+5V	Output or Input	5V Output (From On-board Regulator) or 5V (Input from External Power Supply)
28	RESET	Input	Reset
29	GND	Power	Supply Ground
30	VIN	Power	Supply voltage

Table 2: 3.2.2 ICSP Pin Description

Arduino Nano ICSP Pin Name	Type	Function
MISO	Input or Output	Master In Slave Out
Vcc	Output	Supply Voltage
SCK	Output	Clock from Master to Slave
MOSI	Output or Input	Master Out Slave In
RST	Input	Reset
GND	Power	Supply Ground

3.3 MPU6050 Gyroscope Sensor Module

3.3.1 Introduction

Fig 3.3:MPU6050 Gyroscope Sensor Module

MPU6050 Module

MPU6050 sensor module is complete 6-axis Motion Tracking Device. It combines 3-axis Gyroscope, 3-axis Accelerometer and Digital Motion Processor all in small package. Also, it has additional feature of on-chip Temperature sensor. It has I2C bus interface to communicate with the microcontrollers.

It has Auxiliary I2C bus to communicate with other sensor devices like 3-axis Magnetometer, Pressure sensor etc.

If 3-axis Magnetometer is connected to auxiliary I2C bus, then MPU6050 can provide complete 9-

axis Motion Fusion output.

Let's see MPU6050 inside sensors.

3.3.2 Axis Gyroscope

The MPU6050 consist of 3-axis Gyroscope with Micro Electro Mechanical System(MEMS) technology. It is used to detect rotational velocity along the X, Y, Z axes as shown in below figure.

MPU-6050 Orientation & Polarity of Rotation

Fig 3.4:Axis Gyroscope

- When the gyros are rotated about any of the sense axes, the Coriolis Effect causes a vibration that is

detected by a MEM inside MPU6050.

- The resulting signal is amplified, demodulated, and filtered to produce a voltage that is proportional to the angular rate.
- This voltage is digitized using 16-bit ADC to sample each axis.
- The full-scale range of output are +/- 250, +/- 500, +/- 1000, +/- 2000.
- It measures the angular velocity along each axis in degree per second unit.

3.3.3 Axis Accelerometer

The MPU6050 consist 3-axis Accelerometer with Micro Electro Mechanical (MEMs) technology. It used to detect angle of tilt or inclination along the X, Y and Z axes as shown in below figure.

Fig 3.5: Axis Accelerometer

- Acceleration along the axes deflects the movable mass.
- This displacement of moving plate (mass) unbalances the differential capacitor which results in sensor output. Output amplitude is proportional to acceleration.
- 16-bit ADC is used to get digitized output.
- The full-scale range of acceleration are +/- 2g, +/- 4g, +/- 8g, +/- 16g.
- It measured in g (gravity force) unit.
- When device placed on flat surface it will measure 0g on X and Y axis and +1g on Z axis.

3.3.4 DMP (Digital Motion Processor)

The embedded Digital Motion Processor (DMP) is used to compute motion processing algorithms. It takes data from gyroscope, accelerometer and additional 3rd party sensor such as magnetometer and processes the data. It provides motion data like roll, pitch, yaw angles, landscape and portrait sense etc. It minimizes the processes of host in computing motion data. The resulting data can be read from DMP registers.

3.3.5 On-chip Temperature Sensor

On-chip temperature sensor output is digitized using ADC. The reading from temperature sensor can be read from sensor data register.

3.3.6 MPU-6050 Module

Fig 3.6:MPU-6050 Module

The MPU-6050 module has 8 pins,

INT: Interrupt digital output pin.

AD0: I2C Slave Address LSB pin. This is 0th bit in 7-bit slave address of device. If connected to VCC then it is read as logic one and slave address changes.

XCL: Auxiliary Serial Clock pin. This pin is used to connect other I2C interface enabled sensors SCL pin to MPU-6050.

XDA: Auxiliary Serial Data pin. This pin is used to connect other I2C interface enabled sensors SDA pin to MPU-6050.

SCL: Serial Clock pin. Connect this pin to microcontrollers SCL pin.

SDA: Serial Data pin. Connect this pin to microcontrollers SDA pin.

GND: Ground pin. Connect this pin to ground connection.

VCC: Power supply pin. Connect this pin to +5V DC supply.

MPU-6050 module has Slave address (When AD0 = 0, i.e. it is not connected to Vcc) as,

Slave Write address(SLA+W): 0xD0

Slave Read address(SLA+R): 0xD1

MPU-6050 has various registers to control and configure its mode of operation. So, kindly go through [MPU-6050 datasheet](#) and [MPU-6050 Register Map](#).

3.3.7 Calculations

Note that gyroscope and accelerometer sensor data of MPU6050 module consists of 16-bit raw data in 2's complement form.

Temperature sensor data of MPU6050 module consists of 16-bit data (not in 2's complement form).

Now suppose we have selected,

- Accelerometer full scale range of +/- 2g with Sensitivity Scale Factor of 16,384 LSB(Count)/g.
- Gyroscope full scale range of +/- 250 °/s with Sensitivity Scale Factor of 131 LSB (Count)/°/s.

Then,

To get sensor raw data, we need to first perform 2's complement on sensor data of Accelerometer and gyroscope.

After getting sensor raw data we can calculate acceleration and angular velocity by dividing sensor raw data with their sensitivity scale factor as follows,

Accelerometer values in g (g force)

Acceleration along the X axis = (Accelerometer X axis raw data/16384) g.

Acceleration along the Y axis = (Accelerometer Y axis raw data/16384) g.

Acceleration along the Z axis = (Accelerometer Z axis raw data/16384) g.

Gyroscope values in °/s (degree per second)

Angular velocity along the X axis = (Gyroscope X axis raw data/131) °/s.

Angular velocity along the Y axis = (Gyroscope Y axis raw data/131) °/s.

Angular velocity along the Z axis = (Gyroscope Z axis raw data/131) °/s.

Temperature value in °c (degree per Celsius)

Temperature in degrees C = ((temperature sensor data)/340 + 36.53) °c.

For example,

Suppose, after 2' complement we get accelerometer X axes raw value = +15454

Then $A_x = +15454/16384 = 0.94$ g.

3.4 BUZZER

A **buzzer** or **beeper** is an audio signalling device, which may be mechanical , electromechanical, or piezoelectric (piezo for short). Typical uses of buzzers and beepers include alarm devices, timers, and confirmation of user input such as a mouse click or keystroke.

Fig 3.7: Buzzer

3.4.1 History

Electromechanical

The electric buzzer was invented in 1831 by Joseph Henry. They were mainly used in early doorbells until they were phased out in the early 1930s in favor of musical chimes, which had a softer tone.

Piezoelectric

Piezoelectric buzzers, or piezo buzzers, as they are sometimes called, were invented by Japanese manufacturers and fitted into a wide array of products during the 1970s to 1980s. This advancement mainly came about because of cooperative efforts by Japanese manufacturing companies. In 1951, they established the Barium Titanate Application Research Committee, which allowed the companies to be "competitively cooperative" and bring about several piezoelectric innovations and inventions.

3.4.2Types

Electromechanical

Early devices were based on an electromechanical system identical to an electric bell without the metal gong. Similarly, a relay may be connected to interrupt its own actuating current, causing the contacts to buzz. Often these units were anchored to a wall or ceiling to use it as a sounding board. The word "buzzer" comes from the rasping noise that electromechanical buzzers made.

Mechanical

A joy buzzer is an example of a purely mechanical buzzer and they require drivers. Other examples of them are doorbells.

Piezoelectric

A piezoelectric element may be driven by an oscillating electronic circuit or other audio signal source, driven with a piezoelectric audio amplifier. Sounds commonly used to indicate that a button has been pressed are a click, a ring or a beep.

A piezoelectric buzzer/beeper also depends on acoustic cavity resonance or Helmholtz resonance to produce an audible beep.

3.4.3 Modern applications

While technological advancements have caused buzzers to be impractical and undesirable^[citation needed], there are still instances in which buzzers and similar circuits may be used. Present day applications include:

- Novelty uses
- Judging panels
- Educational purposes
- Annunciator panels
- Electronic metronomes
- Game show lock-out device
- Microwave ovens and other household appliances
- Sporting events such as basketball games
- Electrical alarms
- Joy buzzer (mechanical buzzer used for pranks)

3.4.4 Piezo Buzzer Characteristics

- Wide operating voltage: 3~250 V
- Lower current consumption: less than 30 mA higher rated frequency
- Larger footprint
- Higher sound pressure level

Fig 3.8: Piezo Buzzer

3.4.5 Piezoceramic Element Structure

Fig: Piezoceramic Element Structure

At the heart of all piezo-type buzzers is the piezoelectric element. The piezoelectric element is composed of a piezoelectric ceramic and a metal plate held together with adhesive. Both sides of the piezoelectric ceramic plate contain an electrode for electrical conduction. Piezo materials exhibit a specific phenomenon known as the piezoelectric effect and the reverse piezoelectric effect. Exposure to mechanical strain will cause the material to develop an electric field, and vice versa.

3.4.7 Working Principle of Piezo Buzzers

Fig 3.10: Working Principle of Piezo Buzzers

When an alternating voltage is applied to the piezoceramic element, the element extends and shrinks diametrically. This characteristic of piezoelectric material is utilized to make the ceramic plate vibrate rapidly to generate sound waves.

3.4.8 Piezo Buzzer Structure

Fig 3.11: Piezo Buzzer Structure

There are two types of piezo buzzers - transducers and indicators. Transducers consist of a casing, a piezoceramic element and a terminal. In order to operate a transducer, the user must send a square wave signal to the buzzer. Indicators consist of a casing, a piezoceramic element, a circuit board and a terminal. In order to operate an indicator, the user must send the buzzer a specified dc voltage.

3.4.9 Piezo Buzzer Feedback

Some CUI Devices piezo buzzers include a feedback line. Driving circuits for buzzers with feedback tend to be simpler than those circuits without. Feedback is accomplished by dividing the piezo element into two, electrically isolated pieces. When the main piezo element is actuated it squeezes the feedback portion, creating a voltage on the feedback line. A simple way to use feedback is to have the feedback line connected to the base of a transistor. As the piezo element oscillates, the feedback signal will oscillate and the transistor will alternately block or allow current to flow.

- The feedback line provides a voltage that is proportional to the strain on the main piezo element
- This voltage can be used to create a simple, self-oscillating circuit

3.4.10 How to use a Buzzer

A buzzer is a small yet efficient component to add sound features to our project/system. It is very small and compact 2-pin structure hence can be easily used on breadboard, Perf Board and even on PCBs which makes this a widely used component in most electronic applications.

There are two types are buzzers that are commonly available. The one shown here is a simple buzzer which when powered will make a Continuous Beeeeeeppp.... sound, the other type is called a readymade buzzer which will look bulkier than this and will produce a Beep. Beep. Beep. Sound due to the internal oscillating circuit present inside it. But, the one shown here is most widely used because it can be customised with help of other circuits to fit easily in our application.

This buzzer can be used by simply powering it using a DC power supply ranging from 4V to 9V. A simple 9V battery can also be used, but it is recommended to use a regulated +5V or +6V DC supply. The buzzer is normally associated with a switching circuit to turn ON or turn OFF the buzzer at required time and require interval.

3.5 SIM800L GSM Module

Fig 3.14 SIM800L GSM Module

3.5.1 Hardware Overview of SIM800L GSM/GPRS module

At the heart of the module is a SIM800L GSM cellular chip from SimCom. The operating voltage of the chip is from 3.4V to 4.4V, which makes it an ideal candidate for direct LiPo battery supply. This makes it a good choice for embedding into projects without a lot of space.

Fig 3.16: Hardware Overview of SIM800L GSM/GPRS module

All the necessary data pins of SIM800L GSM chip are broken out to a 0.1" pitch headers. This includes pins required for communication with a microcontroller over UART. The module supports baud rate from 1200bps to 115200bps with Auto-Baud detection.

The module needs an external antenna to connect to a network. The module usually comes with a Helical Antenna and solders directly to NET pin on PCB. The board also has a U.FL connector facility in case you want to keep the antenna away from the board. There's a SIM socket on the back!

Fig 3.15: Hardware Overview of SIM800L GSM/GPRS module

Any activated, 2G micro SIM card would work perfectly. Correct direction for inserting SIM card is normally engraved on the surface of the SIM socket.

This module measures only 1 inch² but packs a surprising amount of features into its little frame. Some of them are listed below:

Supports Quad-band: GSM850, EGSM900, DCS1800 and PCS1900

Connect onto any global GSM network with any 2G SIM

Make and receive voice calls using an external 8Ω speaker & electret microphone

Send and receive SMS messages

Send and receive GPRS data (TCP/IP, HTTP, etc.)

Scan and receive FM radio broadcasts

Transmit Power:

Class 4 (2W) for GSM850

Class 1 (1W) for DCS1800
Serial-based AT Command Set
FL connectors for cell antennae
Accepts Micro SIM Card

3.7 Arduino IDE

Arduino Software IDE

Fig. 3.16 Screenshot of Arduino IDE showing *Blink* program

The **Arduino Integrated Development Environment (IDE)** is a cross-platform application (for Windows, macOS, Linux) that is written in functions from C and C++^[2]. It is used to write and upload programs to Arduino compatible boards, but also, with the help of 3rd party cores, other vendor development boards.^[24]

The source code for the IDE is released under the GNU General Public License, version 2.^[25] The Arduino IDE supports the languages C and C++ using special rules of code structuring.^[26] The Arduino IDE supplies a software library from the Wiring project, which provides many common input and output procedures. User-written code only requires two basic functions, for starting the sketch and the main program loop, that are compiled and linked with a program stub *main()* into an executable cyclic executive program with the GNU toolchain, also included with the IDE distribution.^[27] The Arduino IDE employs the program *avrdude* to convert the executable code into a text file in hexadecimal encoding that is loaded into the Arduino board by a

loader program in the board's firmware.^[28] By default, avrdude is used as the uploading tool to flash the user code onto official Arduino boards^[29].

With the rising popularity of Arduino as a software platform, other vendors started to implement custom open source compilers & tools (cores) that can build and upload sketches to other MCUs that are not supported by Arduino's official line of MCUs.

In October 2019 the Arduino organization began providing early access to a new Arduino Pro IDE with debugging^[30] and other advanced features.^[31]

3.8.1 Proteus Design Suite

Proteus Design Suite

A screenshot of Proteus Design Suite

<u>Developer(s)</u>	Labcenter Electronics Ltd.
<u>Initial release</u>	1988
<u>Stable release</u>	8.10
<u>Operating system</u>	Windows
<u>Type</u>	<u>Electronic design automation</u>
<u>Licence</u>	<u>Proprietary</u>

Website www.labcenter.com

The **Proteus Design Suite** is a proprietary software tool suite used primarily for electronic design automation. The software is used mainly by electronic design engineers and technicians to create schematics and electronic prints for manufacturing printed circuit boards.

It was developed in Yorkshire, England by Labcenter Electronics Ltd and is available in English, French, Spanish and Chinese languages.

3.8.2 History

The first version of what is now the Proteus Design Suite was called PC-B and was written by the company chairman, John Jameson, for DOS in 1988. Schematic Capture support followed in 1990, with a port to the Windows environment shortly thereafter. Mixed mode SPICE Simulation was first integrated into Proteus in 1996 and microcontroller simulation then arrived in Proteus in 1998. Shape based autorouting was added in 2002 and 2006 saw another major product update with 3D Board Visualisation. More recently, a dedicated IDE for simulation was added in 2011 and MCAD import/export was included in 2015. Support for high speed design was added in 2017. ^[35] Feature led product releases are typically biannual, while maintenance based service packs are released as it is required.

3.8.3 Product Modules

The Proteus Design Suite is a Windows application for schematic capture, simulation, and PCB (Printed Circuit Board) layout design. It can be purchased in many configurations, depending on the size of designs being produced and the requirements for microcontroller simulation. All PCB Design products include an autorouter and basic mixed mode SPICE simulation capabilities.

3.8.4 Schematic Capture

Schematic capture in the Proteus Design Suite is used for both the simulation of designs and as the design phase of a PCB layout project. It is therefore a core component and is included with all product configurations.

3.8.5 Microcontroller Simulation

The micro-controller simulation in Proteus works by applying either a hex file or a debug file to the microcontroller part on the schematic. It is then co-simulated along with any analog and digital electronics connected to it. This enables its use in a broad spectrum of project prototyping in areas such as motor control,^{[36][37]} temperature control^{[4][5]} and user interface design.^[6] It also finds use in the general hobbyist community^{[38][39]} and, since no hardware is required, is convenient to use as a training^{[40][41]} or teaching tool.^{[11][12]} Support is available for co-simulation of:

- Microchip Technologies PIC10, PIC12, PIC16, PIC18, PIC24, dsPIC33 Microcontrollers.
- Atmel AVR (and Arduino), 8051 and ARM Cortex-M3 Microcontrollers
- NXP 8051, ARM7, ARM Cortex-M0 and ARM Cortex-M3 Microcontrollers.
- Texas Instruments MSP430, PICCOLO DSP and ARM Cortex-M3 Microcontrollers.
- Parallax Basic Stamp, Freescale HC11, 8086 Microcontrollers.

3.8.6 PCB Design

The PCB Layout module is automatically given connectivity information in the form of a netlist from the schematic capture module. It applies this information, together with the user specified design rules and various design automation tools, to assist with error free board design. PCB's of up to 16 copper layers can be produced with design size limited by product configuration.

3.8.7 3D Verification

The 3D Viewer module allows the board under development to be viewed in 3D together with a semi-transparent height plane that represents the boards enclosure. STEP output can then be used to transfer to mechanical CAD software such as Solid works or Autodesk for accurate mounting and positioning of the board.

CHAPTER 4

DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

4.1 Design

There are three steps involved in this **Design and Implementation of IOT based wheelchair fall detection** Project. These are described below----

4.2 Block diagram

Methodology for achieving goal (Block Diagram)

Fig 4.2: Block diagram

4.3 Flow chart of Design and Implementation

Fig 4.1 Flow chart of Design and Implementation

4.4 Implementation

Fig 4.3: Implementation

4.4 Working Principle

The accelerometer sensor is used to find the acceleration and gyroscope is used to detect the fall with the help of velocity angle and it maintains a threshold value if the value exceeds the limit it is considered as a fall. Secondly it consists of Wi-Fi module and that is used to transfer the message through internet. GPS module is used in sharing the location in case the fall is occurred the message already stored. There is a buzzer button it will give alarm when the fall occurred suppose it gives alarm for fall like activities the elderly people can off the buzzer button so the alert message will not be sent to the nearby people. The tri axial accelerometer is used to find the body postures. The angle information is obtained from the three axis and it differs from different postures. The different value generated from the three axis is taken in different pins by selecting only

one signal at a time. The obtained signal is converted in to digital format with the help of analog to digital converter, and then the obtained digital values are compared to the static threshold values present. The positions value obtained is delayed by 23% in order to reduce the false positive produced. Wi-Fi module is used to send an alert message to the nearby contacts of the elderly people and help them. The messaging contacts are saved before. The micro controller and the Wi-Fi module is charged using an USB cable and the charge produced to the every parts of the controller.

4.5 Circuit diagram

Fig 4.5: Circuit diagram

CHAPTER 5

FUTURE WORK AND CONCLUSION

Increased awareness of the occurrence of falls among the elderly and enrollment of efforts to prevent or diminish such events are highly needed in order to improve the quality of life for elderly people and provide them with convenient fall detection and prevention techniques. Despite the considerable achievements that have been accomplished on the field of providing multiple solutions for elderly fall monitoring, detection, and prevention in the recent years, there are still some clear challenges to overcome.

Typically, drawbacks previously stated while surveying various types of research and commercial fall detection and prevention solutions, are considered as open issues that have to be considered for further research.

Also, regarding detection of falls using camera-based surveillance and image processing techniques , there still some difficulties to overcome. One of those difficulties is the fact that visual fall detection is inherently prone to high levels of false fall detection as what appears to be a fall might not be a real fall, but a deliberate movement towards the ground.

In other words, most of current systems are unable to discriminate between real fall incident and an event when person is lying or sitting down abruptly. Also, existent fall detection systems tend to deal with restricted movement patterns and fall incidents to be detected, whereas in real indoor environments various normal/abnormal motions occur.

Other systems, as in , used the audio information or using 3D trajectory and speed of head to infer events.

These mechanisms tend to be more complex and need extra additional costs. Moreover, using the accelerometer sensor technology integrated in smart phones for fall detection has numerous advantages in cost and capability of the system . However, unfortunately, it may be difficult to convince users to mount the phone to various body parts in order to improve fall detection rate .

Also, actions such as raising the phone to the user's ear to start a call and lowering the phone from the user's ear to end a call may highly affect the phone's ability of having correct fall detection.

So, the software applications must dynamically adjust to different locations and methods of carrying the phone. This requires the software to classify acceleration parameters of general use to identify the correct parameters for the fall detection logic. Furthermore, the area of behavior determination, which is focused on building a behavioral profile of the aging patient and monitoring deviations appearance from the model, is still widely open for further research work.

Behavior determination is heavily based on activity recognition and location tracking that detects a typical behavior, which might be caused by decreased health status, progressing disease, or emergency situation . Another challenge is that despite understanding to a great extent the causes of most falls, there is still no many methods to accurately predict that a fall event is likely to occur.

Generally, all monitoring algorithms and approaches for fall detection and prevention relying on only one data provider (movement-sensor, camera, accelerometer, etc.) have their own limitations and do not ensure 100% reliability . In fact, preventing falls and injuries is difficult because they are complex events caused by a combination of intrinsic impairments and disabilities with or without accompanying environmental conditions. Algorithms for fall detection for several environments and the subject's physical condition were rather troublesome; however, a combination of movement sensors and signal-processing technologies can provide more accurate and precise fall detection and prevention approaches.

Data fusion based on multi-sensing technology offers many challenges for providing more accurate approaches for fall detection and prevention. Multi-sensor data fusion is the area focusing on creating multi-modal systems, which receive data from several providers and perform correlation or fusion upon it in order

to increase the accuracy and reliability of the proposed systems. Moreover, combining multi-sensing data fusion technology with prediction technologies such as Machine Learning and

Artificial Intelligence approaches will support developing intelligent fall prevention system based on fall prediction.

Finally, elderly people in long-term care centers or aging persons with cognitive impairment, who have not widely considered in this survey, are as well at high risk of falling and more specialized technology solutions must be developed specifically for these populations.

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APENDIX

```
#include <SoftwareSerial.h>
#include <Wire.h>
SoftwareSerial gsm(10, 11); //ARDU RX, TX -> BT TX, RX
#define gsm Serial
#define MPU_addr 0x68
#define buzz A1
#define relay A2
#define butt1 7
#define butt2 8
#define butt3 9
#define butt4 4
#define butt5 5
#define butt6 6
#define led 13
#define LOCATION "\nLink: https://www.google.com/maps/place/68+Rd+06,+Chittagong/"
//define LOCATION "\nLink:
https://www.google.com/maps/place/22%C2%B021'32.4%22N+91%C2%B048'36.7%22E"
//define LOCATION "\nLink: https://www.google.com/maps/place/22.6177925,91.6593439"
//define LOCATION "\nLink: https://www.google.com/maps/place/22.4100936,91.8147923"
#define number1 "01849821296"
#define number2 "01864851400"
#define number3 "01833905966"
int count;
bool smsFlag = 0;
void setup() {
  Serial.begin(9600);
  gsm.begin(9600);
  Wire.begin();
  Wire.beginTransmission(MPU_addr);
  Wire.write(0x6B);
```

```

Wire.write(0);
Wire.endTransmission(true);
pinMode(buzz, OUTPUT);
pinMode(relay, OUTPUT);
pinMode(butt1, INPUT_PULLUP);
pinMode(butt2, INPUT_PULLUP);
pinMode(butt3, INPUT_PULLUP);
pinMode(butt4, INPUT_PULLUP);
pinMode(butt5, INPUT_PULLUP);
pinMode(butt6, INPUT_PULLUP);
pinMode(led, OUTPUT);
digitalWrite(led, 0);
GSMinit();
//getLocation();
digitalWrite(led, 1);
}
void loop() {
  int gas = analogRead(A1);
  bool fall = readGyro();
  digitalWrite(relay, 1);
  if (fall) count++;
  else count = 0;
  if (count > 30 && count < 50) digitalWrite(buzz, 1); // adjust time
  else if (count > 50) { // adjust time
    digitalWrite(relay, 0);
    sendSMS3("Fall Detected.");
    digitalWrite(buzz, 0);
    while(fall) fall = readGyro();
  }
  if (gas > 200) {
    digitalWrite(buzz, 1);
    digitalWrite(relay, 0);
  }
}

```

```

    sendSMS3("Fall Detected.");
    digitalWrite(buzz, 0);
    while (gas > 200) gas = analogRead(A0);
}
if (!digitalRead(butt4)) {
    digitalWrite(buzz, 1);
    digitalWrite(relay, 0);
    sendSMS3("Fall Detected.");
    digitalWrite(buzz, 0);
    while (!digitalRead(butt4));
}
if (!digitalRead(butt5)) {
    digitalWrite(buzz, 1);
    digitalWrite(relay, 0);
    sendSMS3("Fire Detected.");
    digitalWrite(buzz, 0);
    while (!digitalRead(butt5));
}
if (!digitalRead(butt6)) {
    digitalWrite(buzz, 1);
    digitalWrite(relay, 0);
    sendSMS3("LPG Detected.");
    digitalWrite(buzz, 0);
    while (!digitalRead(butt6));
}
Serial.println((String)"B4:" + digitalRead(butt4) + "\tB5:" + digitalRead(butt5)
    + "\tB6:" + digitalRead(butt6) + "\tF:" + fall + "\tG:" + gas + "\tTime:" + count);
delay(100);
}
bool readGyro() {
    int AcX, AcY, AcZ, Tmp, GyX, GyY, GyZ;
    Wire.beginTransaction(MPU_addr);

```

```

Wire.write(0x3B);
Wire.endTransmission(false);
Wire.requestFrom(MPU_addr, 14, true);
AcX = Wire.read() << 8 | Wire.read();
AcY = Wire.read() << 8 | Wire.read();
AcZ = Wire.read() << 8 | Wire.read();
Tmp = Wire.read() << 8 | Wire.read();
GyX = Wire.read() << 8 | Wire.read();
GyY = Wire.read() << 8 | Wire.read();
GyZ = Wire.read() << 8 | Wire.read();
AcX = map(AcX, -32768, 32767, -90, 90);
//GyY = map(GyY, -32768, 32767, -90, 90);
//GyZ = map(GyZ, -32768, 32767, -90, 90);
//Serial.println((String)"X: " + AcX);
if (AcX < -10 || AcX > 10) return true;
else return false;
}
void GSMinit() {
  delay(5000);
  gsm.println("AT");
  response();
  gsm.println("ATE1");
  response();
  gsm.println("AT+CMGF=1");
  response();
  gsm.println("AT+CNMI=1,2,0,0,0");
  response();
  // gsm.println(F("AT+CGATT=1"));
  // response();
  // gsm.println(F("AT+SAPBR=3,1,\"CONTYPE\",\"GPRS\""));
  // response();
  // gsm.println(F("AT+SAPBR=3,1,\"APN\",\"internet\""));

```

```

// response();
// gsm.println("AT+SAPBR=1,1");
// response();
// delay(6000);
// gsm.println("AT+HTTPINIT");
// response();
}

void sendSMS3(String txt) {
  Serial.println("Sending SMS 1.");
  sendSMS(number1, (String)txt + LOCATION);
  Serial.println("Sending SMS 2.");
  sendSMS(number2, (String)txt + LOCATION);
  Serial.println("Sending SMS 3.");
  sendSMS(number3, (String)txt + LOCATION);
  smsFlag = 1;
}

void sendSMS(String number, String txt) {
  gsm.print("AT+CMGF=1\r\n");
  response();
  gsm.print("AT+CMGS=\"");
  response();
  gsm.print(number);
  gsm.print("\r\n");
  response();
  gsm.print(txt);
  gsm.write(0x1A);
  gsm.print("\r\n");
  delay(3000);
  response();
}

void response() {
  while (!gsm.available());
}

```

```
if (gsm.available()) {  
    gsm.readString();  
}  
}
```